

On the continuity of weak efficient solutions for parametric vector equilibrium problems

Arunee Jansila¹, Thanatporn Bantaojai² and Tran Quoc Duy^{3*}

¹Mathematics Program, Faculty of Education, Rajabhat Maha Sarakham University, arunee59jan@gmail.com

²Mathematics (EP), Faculty of Education, Valaya Alongkorn Rajabhat University, thanatpornmaths@gmail.com

³Division of Computational Mathematics and Engineering, Institute for Computational Science,

Faculty of Mathematics and Statistics, Ton Duc Thang University,

Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam, tranquocduy@tdt.edu.vn

Abstract

In this paper, we consider parametric vector equilibrium problems in Hausdorff topological vector spaces. Under suitable assumptions, we establish the continuity of weak efficient solution mappings for parametric vector equilibrium problems without imposing monotonicity and containing any information of the solution mappings. These results improve or are different from recent ones in the literature. Some examples are given to illustrate our results.

Keywords: vector equilibrium problem, weak efficient solution, cone-continuity, upper semicontinuity, lower semicontinuity.

*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: tranquocduy@tdt.edu.vn

1 Introduction

Equilibrium problem is known to be a very convenient tool to formulate and investigate various applied problems arising in pure and applied mathematics, transportations, economics, communication systems and other fields. It encompasses many important problems in nonlinear analysis such as optimization, variational inequality, Nash equilibrium, complementarity problems. Inspired by the original paper of Giannessi [6], which extended classical variational inequalities to the case of vector-valued functions, more general equilibrium problems have been extended to the case of vector-valued objective mapping, known as vector equilibrium problems. We refer the reader to [1, 2, 7] and references therein for more information.

For other mathematical models, the existence of solutions to vector equilibrium problems and more general settings is one of the topics attracted the most considerable attention of researchers [3, 4, 11–13]. A relatively new but rapidly developing issue is the stability of solutions including semicontinuity properties in the sense of Hausdorff and Berge. By virtue of a density result and a scalarization technique, Gong and Yao [9] discussed the lower semicontinuity of the efficient solutions for parametric generalized systems with monotone bifunctions in real locally convex Hausdorff topological vector spaces. By using the ideas of Cheng and Zhu [5], Gong [8] established the continuity of the solution set mapping for the mixed parametric monotone

weak vector equilibrium problems of a certain type in topological vector spaces. In order to extend the results in [5, 8], Li and Fang [14] proposed a relaxed assumption of strict C -mappings related to monotonicity properties and employed it to study the lower semicontinuity of the weak vector solutions and global vector solutions to a parametric generalized Ky Fan inequality. It is worth noting that the monotonicity of mappings may yield that the set of solutions is a singleton. Taking this observation into account, Zhang et al. [18] introduced Hölder-related assumptions to establish the lower semicontinuity of the efficient and weak solution mappings for parametric vector equilibrium problems without using the assumptions related to monotonicity. However, Hölder-related assumption is not natural and hard to apply in practical situations because it require to know the information regarding solution set of the reference problem. Note further that the objective mappings in the mentioned papers above were always imposed to be continuous.

Motivated and inspired by above observations, we consider relaxed versions of upper and lower semicontinuity for vector-valued mappings, which correspond to a generalization of ordinary upper and lower semicontinuity on real-valued functions. This relaxation was also proposed in [15, 17]. For vector-valued mappings with this generalized semicontinuity, we establish the continuity of weak efficient solution mappings for parametric vector equilibrium problems under some new conditions with neither monotonicity

properties nor any information of the solution mappings.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we introduce the weak efficient solutions to parametric vector equilibrium problems, recall some concepts and their properties. We also consider a generalization of ordinary upper and lower semicontinuity on real-valued mappings to vector-valued mappings, and investigate several properties for the generalized semicontinuity of vector-valued mappings. In Section 3, we discuss the continuity of weak efficient solution mappings for parametric vector equilibrium problems and give some examples to illustrate our results.

2 Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, let X, Y and Z be Hausdorff topological vector spaces, $C \subset Y$ be a pointed closed convex cone with nonempty topological interior. Let K be a nonempty subset of X and $f : K \times K \rightarrow Y$ be a vector-valued mapping. The vector equilibrium problem under question is of

(VEP) finding $\bar{x} \in K$ such that

$$f(\bar{x}, y) \notin -A, \forall y \in K,$$

where $A \cup \{0\}$ is a convex cone in Y .

We consider the parametric vector equilibrium problem under perturbations in terms of perturbing the constraint set K and the objective mapping f by a parameter λ varying on a subset Λ of Z .

(PVEP) finding $\bar{x} \in K(\lambda)$ such that

$$f(\lambda, \bar{x}, y) \notin -A, \forall y \in K(\lambda),$$

where $K : \Lambda \rightrightarrows X$ is a set-valued mapping, $f : \Lambda \times X \times X \rightarrow Y$ is a vector-valued mapping.

A vector $x \in K(\lambda)$ is said to be an *weak efficient solution* to (PVEP) if

$$f(\lambda, x, y) \notin -\text{int} C, \forall y \in K(\lambda).$$

By $S(\lambda)$ we denote the set of weak efficient solutions to the problem (PVEP). In this paper, we focus on the continuity of solution mapping S and we always assume that $S(\lambda)$ is nonempty for each λ in a neighborhood of the reference point.

Next we introduce the concepts of upper semicontinuity and lower semicontinuity for vector-valued mappings, which are generalizations of ordinary upper semicontinuity and lower semicontinuity on real-valued functions.

Definition 2.1 Let X, Y be topological vector spaces and C be a pointed solid convex cone in Y . A mapping $g : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be

1. *C-upper semicontinuous* (C -usc in short) at \bar{x} if, for any neighborhood V of the origin in Y , there exists a neighborhood U of \bar{x} such that

$$g(x) \in g(\bar{x}) + V - C, \quad \forall x \in U.$$

2. *C-lower semicontinuous* (C -lsc in short) at \bar{x} if, $-g$ is C -upper semicontinuous at \bar{x} .
3. *C-continuous* at \bar{x} if it is both C -usc and C -lsc at \bar{x} .

In the sequel, we say that a mapping holds a certain property on a subset $M \subset X$ if so does it at each point of M . When $M = X$, we omit "in X " in the statement.

Proposition 2.2 Let X, Y, C and g be as in Definition 2.1. Then the following assertions are equivalent.

- (i) g is C -upper semicontinuous.
- (ii) For each $\bar{x} \in X$ and $c \in \text{int}C$, there is a neighborhood U of \bar{x} such that $g(x) \in g(\bar{x}) + c - \text{int}C$, for all $x \in U$.
- (iii) For each $\bar{x} \in X$ and $a \in Y$, $g^{-1}(a - \text{int}C)$ is open.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Let $\bar{x} \in X$, $c \in \text{int}C$ and $V := c - \text{int}C$ be a neighborhood of the origin in Y . Since g is C -upper semicontinuous, then there exists a neighborhood U of \bar{x} such that

$$g(x) \in g(\bar{x}) + V - C, \quad \forall x \in U. \quad (1)$$

It follows from the convexity of C that $-\text{int}C - C = -\text{int}C$. Combining this and taking into account (1), we obtain

$$g(x) \in g(\bar{x}) + c - \text{int}C, \quad \forall x \in U.$$

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii) For each $a \in Y$, let $\bar{x} \in g^{-1}(a - \text{int}C)$, and $c := a - g(\bar{x})$. Obviously, $c \in \text{int}C$, and there is a neighborhood U of \bar{x} such that

$$g(x) \in g(\bar{x}) + c - \text{int}C, \quad \forall x \in U.$$

Hence, $U \subset g^{-1}(g(\bar{x}) + c - \text{int}C)$, i.e., $g^{-1}(a - \text{int}C)$ is open.

(iii) \Rightarrow (i) Let \bar{x} be an arbitrary point in X and V be a neighborhood of the origin in Y . Since C is a pointed solid cone, there is $c \in \text{int}C$ such that $c \in V$. It is worth noting that \bar{x} is an element of the open set $g^{-1}(g(\bar{x}) + c - \text{int}C)$. Thus, there is a neighborhood U of \bar{x} such that $U \subset g^{-1}(g(\bar{x}) + c - \text{int}C)$, which yields that

$$g(x) \in g(\bar{x}) + c - \text{int}C, \quad \forall x \in U.$$

Therefore, $g(x) \in g(\bar{x}) + V - C$, i.e., g is C -upper semicontinuous. \square

We have an analogous result for the C -lower semicontinuity property of a vector-valued mapping.

Proposition 2.3 Let X, Y, C and g be as in Definition 2.1. The following assertions are equivalent.

- (i) g is C -lower semicontinuous.

- (ii) For each $\bar{x} \in X$ and $c \in \text{int}C$, there is an neighborhood U of \bar{x} such that $g(x) \in g(\bar{x}) - c + \text{int}C$, for all $x \in U$.
- (iii) For each $\bar{x} \in X$ and $a \in Y$, $g^{-1}(a + \text{int}C)$ is open.

Next we present some properties for the C -upper and lower semicontinuity of vector-valued mappings.

Proposition 2.4 Let X, Y, C be as in Definition 2.1, f and g be two mappings from X into Y . The following assertions true.

- (i) αf is C -upper semicontinuous (resp., C -lower semicontinuous) for each $\alpha > 0$, if so is f .
- (ii) $f + g$ is C -upper semicontinuous (resp., C -lower semicontinuous), if so are f and g .

Proof. We consider assertion (ii) for the C -upper semicontinuity, the other cases can be claimed similarly. Let f and g be two C -upper semicontinuous mappings. For each $\bar{x} \in X$ and $c \in \text{int}C$, there exist two open neighborhoods U_1 and U_2 of \bar{x} such that

$$f(x) \in f(\bar{x}) + \frac{1}{2}c - \text{int}C, \quad \forall x \in U_1,$$

and

$$g(x') \in g(\bar{x}) + \frac{1}{2}c - \text{int}C, \quad \forall x' \in U_2.$$

Consequently,

$$(f + g)(x) := f(x) + g(x) \in f(\bar{x}) + g(\bar{x}) - c + \text{int}C,$$

for all $x \in U_1 \cap U_2$. Applying Proposition 2.3 (ii), we conclude that $f + g$ is C -upper semicontinuous. We are done. \square

Definition 2.5 Let X, Y, C, g be as in Definition 2.1, and K be a convex subset of X .

- 1. g is said to be C -quasiconcave on K if for $y \in Y, x_1, x_2 \in K, \theta \in [0, 1]$,

$$g(x_1) \in y + C, g(x_2) \in y + C \text{ imply } g(x_\theta) \in y + C,$$
 where $x_\theta = \theta x_1 + (1 - \theta)x_2$;
- 2. g is strictly C -quasiconcave on K if for $y \in Y, x_1, x_2 \in K, x_1 \neq x_2, \theta \in (0, 1)$,

$$g(x_1) \in y + C, g(x_2) \in y + C \text{ imply } g(x_\theta) \in y + \text{int}C,$$
 where $x_\theta = \theta x_1 + (1 - \theta)x_2$.

In a particular case where $Y = \mathbb{R}, C = \mathbb{R}^+$, we get the definitions of quasiconcave and strictly quasiconcave functions in the usual sense.

Definition 2.6 Let X, Y be two topological vector spaces and F be a set-valued mapping from X to Y .

- 1. F is said to be *upper semicontinuous* (usc, shortly) at x_0 if for any open superset U of $F(x_0)$, there is a neighborhood N of x_0 such that $F(x) \subset U$ for all $x \in N$.
- 2. F is said to be *lower semicontinuous* (lsc, shortly) at x_0 if for any open subset U of Y with $F(x_0) \cap U \neq \emptyset$, there is a neighborhood N of x_0 such that for all $x \in N, F(x) \cap U \neq \emptyset$.
- 3. F is said to be *continuous* at x_0 if it is both usc and lsc at x_0 .

The following results play an important role in our analysis.

Lemma 2.7 (See e.g. [10, Proposition 2.5.6 and Proposition 2.5.9]) Let $F : X \rightrightarrows Y$ be a set-valued mapping. Then, the following assertions hold.

- 1. If $F(\bar{x})$ is compact, then F is usc at \bar{x} if and only if for any sequence $\{x_n\} \subset X$ with $x_n \rightarrow \bar{x}$ and $y_n \in F(x_n)$, there is a subsequence $\{y_{n_k}\}$ that converges to some $\bar{y} \in F(\bar{x})$.
- 2. F is lsc at \bar{x} if and only if, for any sequence $\{x_n\} \subset X$ with $x_n \rightarrow \bar{x}$ and $\bar{y} \in F(\bar{x})$, there exists a sequence $\{y_n\}$ of $F(x_n)$ such that $y_n \rightarrow \bar{y}$.

3 Continuity for the weak efficient solution mapping

In this section, we discuss the upper, lower semicontinuity and closedness of the weak vector solution mappings to (PVEP).

Theorem 3.1 Assume that

- (i) K is continuous and compact valued at $\bar{\lambda}$;
- (ii) $f(\bar{\lambda}, \cdot, y)$ is strictly $Y \setminus (-\text{int}C)$ -quasiconcave on X for each $y \in X$;
- (iii) f is C -upper semicontinuous.

Then, the solution map S is usc and closed at $\bar{\lambda}$.

Proof. We first show that S is usc at $\bar{\lambda}$. Suppose to the contrary that there exist an open set U containing $S(\bar{\lambda})$ along with sequence $\{\lambda_n\}$ converging to $\bar{\lambda}$ such that $x_n \in S(\lambda_n) \setminus U$ for all n . Since K is upper semicontinuous at $\bar{\lambda}$ and $K(\bar{\lambda})$ is compact, one can assume that $\{x_n\}$ (or its subsequence) converges to some point \bar{x} in $K(\bar{\lambda})$. We prove that $\bar{x} \in S(\bar{\lambda})$. Otherwise, there is $\bar{y} \in K(\bar{\lambda})$ such that

$$f(\bar{\lambda}, \bar{x}, \bar{y}) \in -\text{int}C. \tag{2}$$

The lower semicontinuity of K at $\bar{\lambda}$ ensures the existence of a sequence of points $y_n \in K(\lambda_n), y_n \rightarrow \bar{y}$. It follows from the fact $x_n \in S(\lambda_n)$ that

$$f(\lambda_n, x_n, y_n) \in Y \setminus -\text{int}C. \tag{3}$$

For each neighborhood B of the origin in Y , there is a balanced neighborhood B_1 of the origin in Y , i.e.,

$-B_1 = B_1$, such that $B_1 \subset B$. Since f is C -upper semicontinuous at $(\bar{\lambda}, \bar{x}, \bar{y})$, there is $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that, for each $n \geq n_0$, one has

$$f(\lambda_n, x_n, y_n) \in f(\bar{\lambda}, \bar{x}, \bar{y}) + B_1 - C. \quad (4)$$

Utilizing the balance property of B_1 and (4), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} f(\bar{\lambda}, \bar{x}, \bar{y}) &\in f(\lambda_n, x_n, y_n) - B_1 + C \\ &= f(\lambda_n, x_n, y_n) + B_1 + C. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Combining (3), (5) and taking into account that C is a convex cone, we arrive at

$$f(\bar{\lambda}, \bar{x}, \bar{y}) \in Y \setminus -\text{int}C + B_1 + C \subset Y \setminus -\text{int}C + B_1.$$

Consequently, $f(\bar{\lambda}, \bar{x}, \bar{y}) \in Y \setminus -\text{int}C + B$. It follows from the arbitrary choice of B and the closedness of $Y \setminus -\text{int}C$ that $f(\bar{\lambda}, \bar{x}, \bar{y}) \in Y \setminus -\text{int}C$, and hence $\bar{x} \in S(\lambda)$, which is impossible as $x_n \notin U$, for all n . Therefore, S is usc at λ .

Now, we show that S is closed at $\bar{\lambda}$. Let an arbitrary sequence $\{x_n\}$ in $S(\lambda_n)$ with $x_n \rightarrow x_0$. Since $x_n \in K(\lambda_n)$, by assumption (i), we get $x_0 \in K(\bar{\lambda})$. Using the same proof as above, we obtain $x_0 \in S(\bar{\lambda})$. The proof is completed. \square

Remark 3.2 Gong [8] considered the parametric weak vector equilibrium problem in which the objective mapping was given under the following form:

$$f(\lambda, x, y) = \varphi(\lambda, x, y) + \psi(\lambda, y) - \psi(\lambda, x), \quad x, y \in K(\lambda),$$

where $\varphi : \Lambda \times K(\lambda) \times K(\lambda) \rightarrow Y$ and $\psi : \Lambda \times K(\lambda) \rightarrow Y$ were mappings. Therefore, this problem is a special case of (PVEP). Moreover, our Theorem 3 strictly improve Theorem 3.1 in [8] because we omit the monotonicity of $\varphi(\lambda, \cdot, \cdot)$ and convexity of $\psi(\lambda, \cdot) + \varphi(\lambda, x, \cdot)$. Note further that the continuity of objective mapping is relaxed to C -upper semicontinuity.

We give here an example to illustrate the applicable of Theorem 3.

Example 3.3 Let $X = Z = \mathbb{R}$, $Y \equiv \mathbb{R}^2$, $C = \mathbb{R}_+^2$, $\Lambda = [0, 1]$, $K(\lambda) = [0, 1]$, and

$$f(\lambda, x, y) = \begin{cases} ((\sin(x - y) + 1) \cos^2(\frac{1}{\lambda})), \\ (x - y + 1) \cos^2(\frac{1}{\lambda}), & \text{if } \lambda \neq 0. \\ ((\sin(x - y) + 1), x - y + 1), & \text{if } \lambda = 0. \end{cases}$$

It is obvious that all assumptions in Theorem 3 are satisfied because K is usc and compact-valued and f is \mathbb{R}_+^2 -upper semicontinuous. Direct computations give us $S(\lambda) = [0, 1]$, which is usc and compact-valued. However, Theorem 3.1 in [8] is not applicable in this case as f is not continuous.

We are now in position to establish the continuity of solution mapping S to (PVEP).

Theorem 3.4 Suppose the following conditions hold

- (i) K is continuous and compact-convex-valued at $\bar{\lambda}$;
- (ii) $f(\bar{\lambda}, \cdot, y)$ is strictly $Y \setminus -\text{int}C$ -quasiconcave on $K(\bar{\lambda})$ for all $y \in K(\lambda)$;
- (iii) f is C -continuous on $\{\bar{\lambda}\} \times K(\bar{\lambda}) \times K(\bar{\lambda})$.

Then, S is continuous at $\bar{\lambda}$.

Proof. It suffices to show that S is lsc at $\bar{\lambda}$. Suppose to the contrary that there exist $x_0 \in S(\bar{\lambda})$ and a neighborhood W_0 of the origin in X such that for any neighborhood U of $\bar{\lambda}$, there is $\lambda \in U$ satisfying

$$S(\lambda) \cap (x_0 + W_0) = \emptyset.$$

Thus, there is a sequence $\{\lambda_n\}, \lambda_n \rightarrow \bar{\lambda}$ such that

$$S(\lambda_n) \cap (x_0 + W_0) = \emptyset, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (6)$$

Now two situations must be considered.

Case 1. $S(\bar{\lambda}) = \{x_0\}$. Take an arbitrary sequence $\{x_n\}$ in $S(\lambda_n)$. It follows from the upper semicontinuity and compact-valuedness of K that $\{x_n\}$ has a subsequence converging to some point \bar{x} in $K(\bar{\lambda})$. Using arguments given in the proof of Theorem 3, we obtain $\bar{x} \in S(\bar{\lambda})$, which implies that $\bar{x} = x_0$. Hence, $x_n \in x_0 + N$ for n sufficiently large which contradicts (6).

Case 2. $S(\bar{\lambda})$ is not a singleton. There exists $\bar{x} \in S(\bar{\lambda})$ satisfying $\bar{x} \neq x_0$. Then, for any $y \in K(\bar{\lambda})$, one has

$$f(\bar{\lambda}, x_0, y) \in Y \setminus -\text{int}C \text{ and } f(\bar{\lambda}, \bar{x}, y) \in Y \setminus -\text{int}C. \quad (7)$$

Since $f_1(\bar{\lambda}, \cdot, y)$ is strictly $(Y \setminus -\text{int}C)$ -quasiconcave on $K(\bar{\lambda})$, for all $t \in (0, 1)$,

$$f(\bar{\lambda}, t\bar{x} + (1 - t)x_0, y) \in \text{int}(Y \setminus -\text{int}C). \quad (8)$$

Putting $x(t) = t\bar{x} + (1 - t)x_0$ implies that $x(t) \in K(\bar{\lambda})$ as K is convex-valued at $\bar{\lambda}$. It is worth noting that for the chosen W_0 , there exist a neighborhood W_1 of the origin in X and $t_0 \in (0, 1)$ satisfying $W_1 + W_1 \subset W_0$ and $x(t_0) \in x_0 + W_1$. Hence,

$$x(t_0) + W_1 \subset x(t_0) + W_1 + W_1 \subset x_0 + W_0.$$

Since $x(t_0) \in K(\bar{\lambda})$ and K is lsc at $\bar{\lambda}$, there is $\bar{x}_n(t_0) \in K(\lambda_n)$ such that $\bar{x}_n(t_0)$ converge to $x(t_0)$. This implies that $\bar{x}_n(t_0) \in x(t_0) + W_1 \subset x_0 + W_0$, for n sufficiently large. Combining this with (6), one has $\bar{x}_n(t_0) \notin S(\lambda_n)$, for all n . This means that there exists $\bar{y}_n \in K(\lambda_n)$ such that $f(\lambda_n, \bar{x}_n(t_0), \bar{y}_n) \in -\text{int}C$, which yields that

$$-f(\lambda_n, \bar{x}_n(t_0), \bar{y}_n) \in C. \quad (9)$$

Since K is usc and compact-valued at $\bar{\lambda}$, one can assume that \bar{y}_n converges to some point $\bar{y} \in K(\bar{\lambda})$ (taking a subsequence if necessary). For each neighborhood B of the origin in Y , there is a balanced neighborhood B_1 of the origin in Y , i.e., $-B_1 = B_1$, such that $B_1 \subset B$. It follows from the C -lower semicontinuous of f that

$$-f(\lambda_n, \bar{x}_n(t_0), \bar{y}_n) \in -f(\bar{\lambda}, x(t_0), \bar{y}) + B_1 - C. \quad (10)$$

Utilizing the balance of B_1 and (10), we get

$$-f(\bar{\lambda}, x(t_0), \bar{y}) \in -f(\lambda_n, \bar{x}_n(t_0), \bar{y}_n) + B_1 + C. \quad (11)$$

In view of (9), (11) and taking into account the convexity of C , we arrive at

$$-f(\bar{\lambda}, x(t_0), \bar{y}) \in C + B_1 + C \subset B + C.$$

This together with the arbitrary choice of B and the closedness of C gives

$$-f(\bar{\lambda}, x(t_0), \bar{y}) \in C,$$

or equivalently, $f(\bar{\lambda}, x(t_0), \bar{y}) \in -C$, which contradicts (8). This brings the proof to the end. \square

Remark 3.5 In the special case mentioned in Remark 3, Theorem 3 improve Theorem 4.1 in [8]. The monotonicity, convexity and continuity of objective mappings are omitted or relaxed. In [16], Peng and Chang discussed the lower semicontinuity of the weak efficient solution mappings for parametric generalized systems under weak assumption related to monotonicity property of objective mapping ($f(\lambda, x, y) + f(\lambda, y, x) \in -\text{int } C$ for all $x, y \in K(\lambda), x \neq y$). Their approach is based on the density property of the solution set. Our approach is different from theirs. Now, we give an example to illustrate the case.

Example 3.6 Let $X = Y = Z = \mathbb{R}$, $C = \mathbb{R}_+$, $\Lambda = [0, 1]$, $K(\lambda) = [\lambda, \lambda + 1]$ and $f(\lambda, x, y) = x^3 + y^3$. Then, all assumptions of Theorem 3 are all satisfied. Hence, our Theorem 3 is applicable and the solution mapping S is lower semicontinuous on Λ (in fact $S(\lambda) = [\lambda, \lambda + 1]$ for all $\lambda \in \Lambda$). However, assumption (iii) of Theorem 3.2 in [16] is violated because $f(\lambda, x, y) + f(\lambda, y, x) = 2(x^3 + y^3) \in C$ for all $x, y \in K(\lambda)$. Therefore, Theorem 3.2 in [16] is not applicable in this case.

4 Conclusion

Under suitable assumptions, we establish the continuity of weak efficient solution mappings for parametric vector equilibrium problems without imposing monotonicity and containing any information of the solution mappings. These results improve or are different from recent ones in the literature. Some examples are given to illustrate the results.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by Rajabhat Maha Sarakham University, Valaya Alongkorn Rajabhat University under the Royal Patronage, Pathumtani, Division of Computational Mathematics and Engineering, Institute for Computational Science, Faculty of Mathematics and Statistics, Ton Duc Thang University, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

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